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Copper(II) Complexes of Caffeine-Diacetate Bis Caffeine Copper(II)

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*Manuscript received 1 March 1977, revised 18 August 1977,
accepted 7 December 1977.*

THE complexes of caffeine with copper nitrate and ruthenium chloride have recently been reported by Biagicingi et al¹ and Krentzien et al² respectively. The present communication reports on the preparation and characterisation of the copper(II) complex, viz. $[\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{caffeine})_2]$ with caffeine. The additional interesting aspect of this complex is its ability to initiate vinyl polymerisation (acrylamide), both photochemically and thermally (70°).

Experimental

The complex was isolated by mixing methanolic solutions of caffeine and copper acetate, in the molar ratio of 2 : 1. The mixture was mechanically stirred at 60° for 90 minutes. The hot contents were then concentrated and crystallised. Bluish green crystals were filtered off, washed with acetone and ether and dried in vacuo.

The complex was analysed for copper content volumetrically. On analysis, the % of Cu, C, H and N are determined to be 10.58%, 40.53%, 4.36%, and 18.9% respectively and the calculated values are 10.81%, 40.82%, 4.42% and 19.05% respectively for the formula $\text{CuC}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_8\text{O}_8$.

Hilger-Watts Uvispec spectrophotometer for absorbance measurements, Perkin-Elmer infracord spectrophotometer for ir spectra, Gouy's magnetic balance for magnetic susceptibility, Philips conductivity bridge type PR 9500 for conductivity and Beckmann Freezing Point apparatus for molecular weight measurements were used.

NMR spectra were obtained in DMSO-d₆ with the Bruker NMR spectrophotometer (TMS as internal reference). The sweepwidth was 500 HZ and the sweeptime 500 sec.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance in methanol at 10⁻³M concentration shows the complex to be a non-elec-

trolyte (11 mhos). The observed magnetic moment of 1.84 B.M. at 300°K for the complex, indicates the presence of one unpaired electron. These data, along with the molecular weight determination in DMSO solution (Found 565 ; calculated 570) suggest the monomeric structure for the complex.

Electronic Spectra :

The variations in different solvents (Table 1) together with the location of the absorption bands at not very high frequency possibly suggest a tetragonally distorted octahedral structure for the complex³.

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR THE COPPER(II) COMPLEX

Solvent	Absorption bands in kK	
H ₂ O	39.00	13.50 ^{br}
CH ₃ OH	39.10	14.00 ^{br}
DMSO		14.50 ^{br}
CH ₃ CN		15.00 ^{br}

Ir Spectra :

In the ir spectra of the complex, the $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ observed at 272 cm⁻¹ bears similarity to the $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ reported in the various copper-imidazole complexes⁴. The symmetric and antisymmetric vibrations of the OCO group which occur at 1420 cm⁻¹ and 1580 cm⁻¹ respectively, indicate the asymmetric bidentate nature of the acetato group.

NMR Spectra :

In caffeine, the PMR absorptions for the three -N-CH₃ groups appear at $\delta=4.1, 3.6$ and 3.4 . The only aromatic proton in the five membered ring of caffeine shows itself at $\delta=7.6$. In the NMR spectrum of the complex, the above three methyl proton signals are not only shifted to lower field, but also broadened with the result that they merge to form a single new peak at $\delta=3.31$. Further, the co-ordination of the N₉ atom of caffeine to the paramagnetic Cu²⁺ ion results in the broadening of the signal at 7.6 so much that it is no longer observed in the complex as supported by the work of Li et al^{5,6,7}

Composition of the Complex :

Lambert Beer's law is obeyed by the complex within the concentration range 50 to 300 ppm. Job's continuous variation method indicated the formation of a 1 : 2 complex.

From the experimental methods described above, we conclude that caffeine behaves as an unidentate ligand with co-ordination to the metal atom through N₉ atom and that the complex can be represented by a tetragonally distorted octahedral structure with asymmetric chelation of the acetato group. This complex seems to be the second reported instance

wherein the dimeric structure of copper acetate has been destroyed⁹.

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Mixed-ligand Complexes of Diamine (salicylato) Cu(II) and Diamine(salicylato) Ni(II) with 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde

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Manuscript received on 7 May 1977, revised 2 September 1977,
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A survey of the literature¹⁻³ has revealed that no work has been done on the mixed-ligand complexes of diamine(salicylato) Cu(II) and diamine (salicylato) Ni(II) with 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde. The present note deals with the mixed-ligand (Schiff base) complexes, synthesised by the interaction of 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with the mixed complexes of the type [ML-1, 3 diaminopropane], where LH_2 = salicylic acid. The resulting mixed-ligand complexes retain (L^{-2}) in their structure while the -OH groups of the Schiff base N-N'-propylene bis(α -methyl-2-hydroxybenzylidene imino) or N-N'-propylene bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde imino) remain unco-ordinated.

The metal salicylates were treated with ethylene diamine or propylene diamine and the diamine (salicylato) Cu(II) and diamine(salicylato) Ni(II) obtained by the following two procedures :

(1) To a mixture of equimolar (1 M) aqueous solution of nickel chloride and salicylic acid in the ratio of 1 : 2, an aqueous solution of 1, 3-diamino propane (1 M) was added till the pH was ~6. After 40-45 minutes a greenish-blue precipitate was

obtained. It was filtered, washed, dried, weighed and analysed. (2) Alternatively bis or tris-(1, 3-diamino propane) nickel(II) chloride (0.5 g) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and to it an aqueous solution of salicylic acid (1 M) was added till pH 6 was attained. After 40 minutes or so a greenish-blue compound obtained, was filtered, washed, dried, weighed and analysed. These compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analysis and based on these data their composition (Fig. 1) may be expressed by [MLA] $2H_2O$, where M = Cu(II) or Ni(II), LH_2 = salicylic acid and A = ethylenediamine or propylene diamine.

Fig. 1. Mixed-ligand Complexes of Diamine (Salicylato) M(II) with 2-Hydroxyacetophenone.

The analysis of the diamine(salicylato) metal(II) indicate them to be the mixed complexes. The water molecules associated with them are lost at 130° suggesting them to be either co-ordinated or water of crystallisation.

These mixed complexes were treated with 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde so that the two -NH₂ groups of the co-ordinated diamine molecule undergo condensation as described below.

A requisite quantity (0.5 g) of the mixed complex was refluxed with 10.0 ml of 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde on a water-bath for 3 hours. The solution was concentrated and the mixed-ligand complex was rendered insoluble by adding an excess of ether in which the unreacted 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde dissolved. The mixed-ligand complex was recrystallised from chloroform. Elemental analysis and molecular weight determinations give the formula [ML-SB] for these compounds, where SB stands for N-N' propylene bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene) or N-N' propylene bis(α -methyl-2-hydroxy benzylidene).

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the mixed-ligand complexes (Fig. 1) suggest the diamagnetic nature of the Ni(II)-complexes⁴ and paramagnetic nature to the extent of one unpaired electron for the Cu(II)-complexes⁵ (1.82 B. M.) at room temperature.

The electronic absorption spectra of the mixed complexes in water and mixed-ligand complexes in chloroform gave absorption peaks in the range of 300-950 nm.